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Executive summary

In the ArcticHubs project, future work aims to create scenarios for hub industries based on identified threats and opportunities in seven Arctic regions, and in addition youth future forum, to explore how the different hub industries are expected to develop across the Arctic by 2035. In addition to construct scenarios, a consistent way is to continue the analysis by evaluating the potential impacts that scenarios possess. Therefore, the main aim of this report is to evaluate the possible scenario impacts, propose concrete steps and responsible actors based on the analysis done together with stakeholders involved in the scenario processes, and with other experts and researchers that answered the evaluation questions.

In the evaluation of the scenario impacts, the used material consists of individual evaluators' reports as well as the scenario reports carried out in each Hub region and future youth forum. The evaluation reports were asked with specified, common questions for all of the Hubs. These questions consisted of following: 1) identifying the main three key drivers affecting the most in Hub region until 2035, 2) identifying the main general impacts of the constructed scenarios, 3) identifying the scenario specific impacts of constructed scenarios on livelihoods, environment, local and indigenous people and culture, new technology introduction, employment, and competence needs, 4) identifying concrete steps and/or measures for reaching desirable future, and 5) identifying responsible parties in society to make the changes and decisions for the desired Arctic futures.

Based on the results, such common impacts as climate change and demographic issues have been identified. Differences exist especially between coastal and inland Hub regions, and such more isolated regions as Greenland. Among the most favoured concrete steps in achieving desirable future in the Arctic are developing education possibilities, involving local communities, enhancing business and investment sectors and making regulations for nature use.

1. Introduction

In the ArcticHubs project, future work aims to create scenarios for hub industries based on identified threats and opportunities in seven Arctic regions, and to explore how the different hub industries are expected to develop across the Arctic by 2035. In addition, the eighth scenario work examines the future views of Arctic youths in the same time frame. In addition to construct scenarios, a consistent way is to continue the analysis by evaluating the potential impacts that scenarios involve. Therefore, the main aim of this report is to evaluate the possible scenario impacts, propose concrete steps and responsible actors together with stakeholders involved in the scenario processes, and with other experts and researchers that answered the evaluation questions.

The overall objective of Work Package 5 (WP5) - Applying ArcticHubs results for creating sustainable future pathways - is to map the futures of the ArcticHubs project regions by complementing existing socio-economic and environmental data, including the data produced in the ArcticHubs WPs 1-4, with the knowledge and views of decision-makers, authorities, economic actors and local residents, including especially indigenous peoples. The earlier scenario work for Task 5.1 was carried out in close cooperation with local community members, with a focus on reconciling different activities to develop desirable future pathways. Deliverable 5.1 summarised the scenarios developed for regions with one or more hub industries, and also combined the future perspectives of different hub industries and indigenous cultural issues across Arctic regions. The evaluation for this deliverable 5.2 was carried out partly in scenario workshops with stakeholders, but also by project's internal and external experts and researchers. The results of both the scenario work and this evaluation will be further discussed with local people in broader future forums in Task 5.4. Based on the whole scenario process in Tasks 5.1, 5.2 and 5.4, policy recommendations will be concluded to decision makers and authorities.

Scenario planning refers to several techniques that aim to construct alternative future developments (preferred, probable and also avoidable futures) based on knowledge of the current situation, i.e. starting from the current situation (see e.g. Van der Heijden, 1996, Bell 1997). Scenarios are hypothetical sequences of events constructed with the intention of drawing attention to causal processes and decision points (Kahn and Wiener, 1967). In

addition to imagining and constructing scenarios, it is very important to assess the impact of the scenarios for different regions and for different hub livelihoods. Scenario construction was carried out through a co-creation process (see D5.1), and scenario impact assessment was carried out in different ways depending on the resources available in each Hub location. Some of the Hubs included the impact assessment in the workshops after the scenarios had been constructed, while others focused on getting feedback with pre-defined questions from researchers and other experts in different sectors of regional development. The overall aim was to identify the potential impacts of the scenarios, to define the preferred future development, and to propose the actual steps and responsible parties needed to achieve the desired future for the development of the various Hubs and the regions as a whole.

In this report we first present some background to the futures studies, then give a brief overview of the scenarios developed in Task 5.1, present the evaluation process and then discuss the results of the evaluation.

1.1. Background for the futures studies

As described in D5.1. futures studies is the systematic study of possible, probable, and preferable futures, and analysis of their potential impacts on society. The methods and tools of futures studies are used to analyse and structure today's problems and challenges in a future-oriented way for decision-making aiming at a systematic, participatory, holistic, future intelligence gathering and medium-to-long-term vision building process (Bell, 1997). The use of futures studies' methods enhances anticipatory consciousness, which in term improves the foresight to be prepared and act faster or earlier, making the organization or individual more effective in dealing with change. The ability to anticipate gives time to better understand threats and opportunities, develop more creative strategies, create new opportunities, and create and share vision for organizational change (Glenn & Gordon, 2009). The value of futures studies is less in forecasting accuracy than in usefulness in planning and opening minds to consider new possibilities and changes in operational environment. Its purpose is not to know the future but to help us make better decisions today via its methods that force us to anticipate opportunities and threats and consider how to address them.

Because of different interests, geopolitical pressures, and socio-economic activities there are many challenges in the future of Arctic land use. The local voices are important to be part of the future plans and decisions, and for discovering the voices futures studies methods can be

successfully used. There are already guidelines and legal norms for improving participation and decision-making processes on land-use planning for Arctic Countries, such as Finland (see e.g. Piipponen & Kurikka, 2020). These include methods like citizen juries, opinion polls, participatory workshops etc in addition to traditional way of taking part in a representative democracy. However, the possibilities and effectiveness of participation vary a lot. As part of the WP 5 research, different in-depth analytical futures research methods are being used and tested to assess understanding of land use conflicts and issues over land. They help to assess drivers and trends impacting the Arctic, local stakeholders, policy makers and citizens' perceptions, and to identify future development opportunities and choices.

2. The constructed scenarios

For the use of scenario impact assessment, the previous task 5.1. (see D5.1) constructed scenario set ups in each of the Hub regions, and in addition in the future youth forum (see Table 1). Altogether eight scenario processes were conducted and the locations, focus of the scenario processes, and constructed scenario names are presented in Table 1. The focus of the scenario processes varied between Hubs as they concentrated on different livelihoods that was first defined by the Hubs' researcher groups. The focus could be specific or more general (such as fish farming and tourism in Westfjords, Iceland or more regional and general such as Inari, Finland) based also on the resources that Hubs scenario process was allocated in the project.

Table 1. The list of locations, foci and constructed scenarios in the ArcticHubs project

Location and countries	The focus of Hubs and regions	The constructed scenarios
1. Inari, Finland	Tourism and indigenous Hub in municipality of Inari, Northern Finland	1. Harmony between clean nature and livelihoods, 2. Land trampled by exploitation and masses, and 3. The middle way - stability through local strengths
2. Northern Finland and Sweden	Forestry Hub in Västerbotten, Norrbotten and Lapland in northern Sweden and Finland, based on Kemi region where bioproduct mill needs wood from the whole area	1. Forestry growth conditioned by green transition, 2. Local drawbacks from external land use control, and 3. Empowered northern communities
3. Malå, Sweden	Forestry, mining and Indigenous Hub in Västerbotten, northern Sweden	1. Focus on growth and 2. Focus on Diversity
4. Suðuroy, Faroe Islands	Tourism and fish farming Hub in Faroes	1. Business-as-usual, 2. Isolation and recession, 3. Alternative sustainability, and 4. Technofix to current problems

5. Nuuk, Greenland	Tourism and Indigenous Hub in Nuuk, Greenland	Resulted in 35 different scenarios, divided by opportunities and threats, all working with five themes: local tourism, the local Greenlandic culture, the local hunting and fishing industry, climate change, and ecologically and culturally sustainable business development
6. Varanger, NO	Fish farming, tourism and indigenous Hub in northern Norway	1. Green growth, 2. Arctic Urbanity, 3. Traditionalist Trap, 4. Ghost Town, and 5. Emerging Coexistence
7. Westfjords, Iceland	Fish farming and tourism hub in northwestern Iceland	1. Transportation infrastructure development, 2. Community-based controlled development of industries, 3. Interaction of economy, infrastructure and transportation, 4. The viability of the communities, 5. Aquaculture-driven community development, and 6. Tourism-driven community development
8. Youth, International	The youth Arctic futures with an emphasis on Indigenous communities	1. What have we done – the crisis of everything and 2. The Arctic Dream

In Table 2 especially the most common themes representing opportunities and threats which have been raised in the context of many regions and hub industries are presented. These themes include nature, climate change, the use of natural resources, global investments, demography, and indigenous issues. The wider description and analysis of these, and in addition the scenario processes, can be found in the D5.1. report.

Table 2. Summary of opportunities and threats.

Theme (+opportunity, - threat)	Nature	Climate change	Natural resource use	Global investments	Demography	Indigenous issues
Scenario process						
Forestry, FI, SE	+ nature-based livelihoods; public access - Green transition threatening	+ increases forest growth and attractiveness of the region; lifestyle change	+ society secures use; locals benefit; resource efficiency increases - disputes	- Green transition investments cause conflicts; wind and solar power profits go outside local communities	+ many "economic legs" attracting more people	
Inari, FI	+ clean, diverse, attractive	+ attraction of mild climate - lack of mitigation; restrictions; increase in pests	+ sustainable policy - unsustainable policy; threat to nature; conflicts	+ investments to the area - Lack of investments; foreign investors with no benefits to locals	+ increase in population along tourism jobs - lack of housing; aging population	+ balance between indigenous rights and freedom of livelihoods; cultural centre for the Sámi; appreciation of the Sámi culture - appropriation of the Sámi culture; land use modes causing problems
Malå, SE	+ nature-based activities	+ climate-smart products; new residents - reindeer husbandry suffers; shorter ski season	+ existence of nat res; sustainable use - exploitation; restrictions	- Benefits go to global corporations		+ good dialogue; Sámi culture profiling the region - cumulative land use effects causing pressure to the Sámi lands
Nuuk, GL	+ way of life - vulnerability	+ more local food	+ zoning for good coexistence; potential - traditions lost; locals neglected	+ foreign investors in harmony with Greenlandic culture - foreign investors		+ development in harmony with Inuit and Greenlandic culture + revivalisation of Inuit culture through tourism - tourism industry prioritized on the cost of indigenous Greenlanders
Suðuroy, FO	+ experiences in nature - carrying capacity	+ multi-trophic aquaculture; changing consumer behavior; domestic tourism; self sufficiency - Extreme weather events; air traffic		- Foreign and outside investors	- aging population	
Varanger, NO	+ nature-based activities	+ north-east passage - invasive species	+ new food resources; green transition jobs - difficult to reconcile; overexploitation; competition			
Westfjords, IS	+ conservation; attraction	- cc as such			+ nature attracts new residents - depopulation	
Youth, INT	+ nature conservation - nature suffering	- refugees; extreme weather events; uncertainty	+ recycling - increase in demand; conflicts		+ remote work attracts returning migrants	+ indig and local peoples' voice heard more - consumerism's negative impact on indig communities

3. The process of the evaluation of scenario impacts in Arctic Hubs project

As mentioned, the resources allocated to the evaluation of scenario impacts varied between Hub regions, and therefore, the scenario impact evaluation process varied too. Some of the Hubs included the impact assessments within the workshops after the scenarios were constructed (such as Inari Hub and Youth Future workshop), and others concentrated on getting feedback with beforehand defined questions from experts on different sectors of regional development and researchers. The overall aim was to identify the potential impacts of scenarios (both general and scenario specific impacts), define the preferred future development, and propose the actual steps and responsible parties needed for reaching the desirable future for the development of various hubs and the regions. In this scenario impact analysis, the material consists of individual evaluation reports as well as the scenario reports carried out in each Hub region and future youth forum.

Regardless of how the evaluation of scenario impacts was conducted (whether it was a more in-depth and participative workshop or more straightforward, asking relevant stakeholder's feedback on scenarios), there were specified, common questions defined for each of the Hubs and youth forum. The scenario evaluation questions from the Hub scenarios point of view were the following:

1. From your Hub point of view, and based on the conducted scenario process, what are **the main three key drivers** affecting the most in your Hub region in the future until 2035 (out of all identified drivers in your Hub scenario process)?
2. What are **the main general impacts** of the constructed scenarios (three positive and three negative impacts regardless of specific scenarios) (e.g. negative impact: Excessive and uncontrolled growth in tourism; positive impact: increasing employment in tourism)?
 - a. What are **the scenario specific impacts** of constructed scenarios on 1) livelihoods, 2) environment, 3) local and indigenous people and culture, 4) new technology introduction, 5) employment, 6) competence needs?
3. When evaluating the identified opportunities and/or desirable futures, what are the **concrete steps and/or measures** for reaching desirable future?
4. Who would be **the responsible actors/parties** in society to make the changes and decisions for the desired Arctic futures?

5. Do you have any **general feedback** on the conducted scenario process in ArcticHubs project?

In addition to these common questions for each Hubs and future youth forum, two experts from BOKU and NORCE – ArcticHubs partner organisations which were not doing the scenario work themselves – were also asked to evaluate the scenario set up as a whole based on the Deliverable 5.1 report. The evaluation questions were the following:

1. From your point of view, what are **the main three key drivers** effecting the Arctic in the future (out of all identified drivers in each of the hubs and regions)?
2. Which of the constructed scenarios are **the most promising for Arctic areas** in achieving the desired futures (e.g. just a list of the presented scenario names with short argument/reason why you selected particularly these scenarios)?
3. From the scenarios point of view (and the identified opportunities and threats) can you identify what are **the concrete steps** to be considered in achieving the desired future?
4. Who would be **the responsible actors** in society to make the changes and decisions for desired Arctic futures?
5. Do you have any **general feedback** on the conducted scenario process in ArcticHubs?

4. Scenario impact assessment reports

4.1. The most promising scenarios selected by the two overall evaluators

The two experts from NORCE and BOKU who evaluated all the scenario reports were asked to evaluate which of the scenarios are the most promising for the future of the Arctic region. The task for them was the following: “Which of the constructed scenarios are the most promising for Arctic areas in achieving the desired futures (e.g. just a list of the presented scenario names with short argument/reason why particularly these scenarios)?” Both evaluators had some reservations for the task. The other one noted that due to the rich variety of cases it was challenging to put the scenarios in prioritized order while the other one regarded the exercise good but thought that the probable futures of the hubs may be different from the desired ones, and she was interested to which scenarios the locals would choose.

The scenarios which both evaluators chose as the most promising ones were (with the argumentation below):

- 1) Inari, Finland (Tourism and indigenous cultures hubs) “The middle way - stability through local strengths”:
 - It appears more pragmatic than the ‘utopian’ scenario and the ‘apocalyptic’ one. This scenario is also in accordance with the objectives of fostering a robust locally embedded economy suitable for adaptation to changes in global trends.
 - It is grounded on current trends and most likely what will happen since the future is dependent in the local community and their agency to create their own future
- 2) Northern Finland and Sweden (Forestry hub) “Empowered northern communities”
 - This is in line with a concern regarding foreign investors and actors. This scenario corresponds to the aspirations of empowering local inhabitants and communities, which make them more resilient in addressing global changes and challenges.
 - Future is decided by the local communities and consequences - good or bad directly affects them
- 3) Malå, Sweden (Forestry hub) “Focus on diversity”:
 - Focus on growth is a problematic discourse in times with global and environmental challenges and also because there is a need for alternative future scenarios that welcome and embrace diversity and the opportunities that are attached to a varied community.
 - Allows for their sustainable growth visions to happen.
- 4) Suðuroy, Faroe Island (Tourism and fish farming hubs) “Alternative sustainability”:

- In line with global trends such as climate change and the need for more alternative ways than business as usual, especially when it comes to large tourism industries/ mass tourism and large- scale fish farming.
 - Goes away from the business-as-usual development and pushes for a more sustainable growth with particular focus on legislation.
- 5) Varanger, Norway (Fish farming, tourism and mining hubs) “Emerging coexistence”
- Focuses on the traditional industries but is still open for innovation and new system alternatives and synergies which is crucial for maintaining a robust and resilient community that can adapt to changes in global food systems, climate change etc.. This scenario does not focus so much on the coexistence between human and ecosystem services, nor the coexistence between minorities and the larger community.
 - Though very difficult to execute, this scenario is the most promising because of the underlying goal of developing together, hopefully not only industries but also the local community and the minorities.
- 6) Westfjords, Iceland (Fish farming and tourism hubs) “Community-based controlled development of industries”:
- Unlike scenarios that solely focuses on either fisheries or tourism, this scenario facilitates diversity through democratic and community-based involvement.
 - Development for the locals by the locals - more transparency and inclusivity in decision making, therefore benefits go to the locals rather than to others.

Selected by evaluator 1 only:

- 1) Nuuk, Greenland (Tourism and indigenous hubs) “Control and monitoring”:
- Mass tourism as a common concern, lack of control, potential influx of foreign investors, and potential lack of local embeddedness. A strategy for mitigating these concerns involves monitoring, regulative tools and control. While tourism development remains a central future scenario, its management in terms of regulations and monitoring is crucial for a sustainable (tourism) development.

The evaluators were unanimous in their selection of most promising scenarios. One of the common nominators seems to be positiveness but also strong emphasis on sustainability and societal development.

4.2. Main key drivers affecting the most in the Arctic in the future

Based on the scenario reports built on workshops and surveys in varying degrees, and the evaluation of scenario impacts by the experts and researchers (Task 5.2), it was possible to identify some common drivers, which seem to have a strong influence to the future of the Arctic. Even though it is obvious, that the hubs of the vast area differ from each other, many

future challenges, drivers and issues are the same in the area. At least **climate change** bringing both positive and negative impacts, increasing **consumption** including different aspects like green transition, technology, resource use and pollution, and **demographic changes** covering both in and out migration from the Arctic, were seen as the key drivers in the Arctic hubs. Indigenous issues will also play a key role in the Arctic future, by identity issues, involving in decision-making, and in land use and resource ownership.

Climate change was pointed out in every report, and it was raised as one of the most important threats in almost all the hubs. Climate change is feared to cause challenges to the local livelihoods, like aquaculture and reindeer herding, and also by shortening the winter tourism seasons. It is feared to weaken the local and indigenous cultures and knowledge. Climate change also seen as a threat in bringing new, harmful species and diseases to the area causing health problems. Warmer weather can also contribute in attracting new industries and jobs, new species or better circumstances for some species. It can boost tourism and contribute to better economy by for example the opening of the North-East Passage. However, climate change was also seen as a positive driver in some aspects according to several hubs. It can for example accelerate the growth of forests and hence enhance the production of forests, and increase the food production, that are important in self-sufficiency which has been pointed out as an important factor in the future.

Tourism is central in all the hubs, even the development and the amount of it differs in different hubs. Tourism is also strongly related to the resource use, and it causes different concerns, for example foreign investors, and problems on nature (erosion), but it also has potential for empowerment and a pathway for desired scenarios. Sustainable tourism is part of this driver where there is no need for resource extraction, but more likely nature experience, silence, and northern lights, are important reasons for visiting the Arctic.

Increasing consumption covers the increasing use of resources, and increased pollution, but also the responses to that like the green transition, and it was pointed out in many of the scenarios as the key driver. Increasing use of resources is inseparable from global investment interest, which are also seen to pose concerns to Arctic Hubs. Development and industrial expansion are being partly done under the concept of green growth, while land use conflicts are intensifying with major societal impacts. In some of the scenarios it is seen critical, that green growth is done sustainably by both ecological, economical, and social means. New opportunities related to technology development will create new industrial solutions and require well educated labor, new types of skill, and possible appeal to the younger generation to settle. Conflicts related to the use of natural resources has been the reality already today in some hubs, but they are seen to increase in the future relation to excessive use of natural resources, and foreign actors and investors. Voices of local population and especially indigenous communities are seen important in the decision-making processes.

Demographic changes in the Arctic are seen as one of the main drivers. Young people and women are seen as groups often underrepresented in the rural Arctic, and people are moving away from the rural areas by better opportunities. In some of the hubs like Nuuk, it is necessary to move away from the whole area. The most rural areas might be facing continuing loss of citizens, but in the future it might be possible that people are moving towards the Arctic by better climatic conditions. Also the availability of labor and skills can play an increasing role in the future where people live. In addition, geopolitics and security were raised as important future drivers in many Hubs.

4.3. Main general impacts of the constructed scenarios

As the key drivers, it seems that also the main general impacts of the different drivers are somewhat the same across the Arctic hubs, even though there are obviously many differences, based on the scenario reports and scenario evaluation reports. Positive impacts were mainly concerning the positive development of the region, and its environment, and community, based on the sustainable management of natural resources, and involving locals in decision-making, as well as to the peaceful coexistence of different livelihoods. In the more negative scenarios, the most prevalent impacts seem to be related mainly to the opposites of the positive ones, but in addition the overtourism or overcrowding of the most popular places seem to be a future threat in almost all the hubs, except for Nuuk, there is no overcrowding of tourism on the site yet, and tourism is just emerging there. Moreover, in some negative scenarios the decisions are made elsewhere, and also the profits of some businesses flow out from the local area, but the negative impacts stay there. The effects of EU regulations is mainly seen as a threat for example in the forestry scenario process, but also positive to the biodiversity, and to the reduction CO2 emissions.

Positive impacts more in detail mentioned in the different scenarios include for example the following: Positive impacts on nature and environment, new innovations and technology, sustainable lifestyle and reduced consumption, resolved conflicts, locals voices being heard more and increased public-participation in decision making, fostering the position of indigenous peoples, increased self-sufficiency, more stable income from tourism, increased accessibility, better economy enhances the economy and services for the locals as well, revitalized remote areas, specialization of regions (like for aquaculture or Sámi culture), achieving a social license to operate, increased tax by tourism benefitting the locals, improved conditions for different livelihoods, and strong communities.

The negative impacts more in detail mentioned in different scenarios included for example excessive and uncontrolled growth in tourism, in and outmigration, and challenges by multiculturalism, increased conflicts both national and international, socio-political conflicts and polarized views, withering of local knowledge and culture, increased stress and mental health problems, traditional livelihoods suffer, decisions made elsewhere, incomes do not stay in the area but all the impacts are suffered there, indigenous rights, nature suffers: environmental impacts like increased CO2, and also reduced development via various reasons.

In Westfjords the development of aquaculture and infrastructure were different from many other hubs, and very important. Improvement in roads is seen important, since it enhances the quality of life of the locals and improves the security, but also can contribute in the tourism industry. It can also reduce the carbon footprint.

In Malå and in the Forestry scenarios (Northern Sweden and Finland), forestry was the most dominant factor, but green transition and climate change are heavily affecting that.

The Arctic Youth had a common idea of the youth having more to say in the decision-making, and also to focus on educating people on things like the environment and different cultures. There was a fear to shift from industrialism to consumerism, which could mean that economic and social disparities intensify.

Suðuroy also has specific future prospects, since it is an island depending on aquaculture and tourism. In Suðuroy it was seen very critical to get the sub-tunnel to increase the connectivity. Tourism is seen as a big opportunity here to also bring new citizens to the area. Also in Suðuroy they are fearing of the over-tourism, but still the most negative effects were seen to come from excessive aquaculture, and focusing on fish farming was seen as a threat to the nature.

Nuuk seems to differ the most from other hubs, because it is an island very isolated from others not offering all the possibilities on the island. In Nuuk tourism is also just emerging, and there are big hopes to the new sources of income. However, in Nuuk they are also concerned about the rapidly changing livelihoods, and adaptation to the tourism industry.

4.4. Specific impacts identified in different Hubs

In the scenario evaluation reports, and the reports of the scenarios of each hub, the specific impacts of each scenario on different issues were identified. Some of the specific impacts were similar in the different hubs, like the impacts of the more negative scenarios on nature and climate for example, and the impacts of the more positive scenarios on the viability of the area, or the position of indigenous and local people. Still, every hub had their own specific impacts as well, depending on the location, demography, and main livelihoods, for example.

Different **livelihoods** were highly abundant in the scenario processes in different hubs. Especially the main land users of the Arctic Hubs, like tourism, mining, aquaculture, and forestry were abundant, both in more negative and more positive scenarios. Especially over-tourism and overcrowding of popular sites seem to be a future threat in many of the scenarios,

like in Inari, and Varanger, but also the effects of large-scale fish farming was seen harmful to the nature for example in Suđuroy and Westfjords. In Nuuk, however tourism is still mainly seen as a positive driver in the future, and the tourism there is just emerging, even though there are some concerns about how it will fit to the local community. In the positive scenarios, tourism is being turned into all-year-round tourism, which is sustainable and nature-based, with more stable income and benefits to the local community. Also, the option of a tourist-tax was pointed out in some of the scenarios.

In the aquaculture Hubs, such as Westfjords, Suđuroy, and Varanger, the development of it was seen positive to the viability of the area and to the population, but the negative effects of it to the local nature and the fjords are concerning in the scenarios. Climate change was mentioned in many scenarios like in Inari, Varanger, and Arctic youth, to have impacts on the livelihoods, mainly the traditional ones. Stable stocks in aquaculture were seen crucial, but climate change was feared to change that. In the negative scenarios this was seen to result in the decline of the local economy, and the well-being of the area diminishes. Also, in other livelihoods based on wildlife like reindeer herding in Inari, the stable populations are seen very important. Overall, the economic drivers are highly dependent on the external factors, like the fluctuations in the global market.

In the Malå and Forestry scenarios, forestry has been pointed out by growing as and sustainable energy source, also because of the climate change effects on forest growth. However, in some scenarios forestry was seen to almost completely phase out since the EU regulations on biodiversity, or the lack of SLO, but it was also seen that the activities for biodiversity and reducing emissions are crucial. In the scenarios, it is seen as a threat that the decisions are made elsewhere, and that is also related to the future where international companies and funding might increasingly come outside from the area or the country. In addition to the traditional livelihoods, the new industries and technology were seen positive, to have positive impacts to the economy and the viability of the area, and by attracting new residents to the region, like in Varanger, and Suđuroy.

In all of the scenarios, the impacts of different futures on **local nature and environment** were raised, and they were both positive and negative. Especially the effect of mass-tourism and cruise ships (Westfjords) was seen to have harmful effects to the nature in the future. The

effect of rising CO₂ emissions, or the ways to reduce them, were also pointed out in the scenarios, and the benefits from carbon sequestration was pointed out for example in the forestry scenarios. The effects of climate change was seen to have impacts on the nature, bring new species, diseases, and pests, and to cause natural disasters, and increase challenges, but also the possibility of the opening of the North-East Passage was seen positive in enabling sustainable transport of good, like sea food, in Varanger, for example.

The importance of a better **transportation and infrastructure** was especially pointed out in the most remote and isolated hubs and islands, like Westfjords and Suđuroy. Better transportation enhances the quality of life of the locals, and improves the security, but it can also contribute to the tourism industry and the competence and stimulate regional development. In Suđuroy, the subtunnel to the island is seen critical in the future to increase the connectivity and the competence of the area, and it's seen as an important driver for all the change and development in the area. However, the harbor development and increasing amount of cruise ships could have a substantial socio-economic impact on local communities and increase the environmental stress. The investments in infrastructure such as road networks are seen important also in Inari.

In many of the hubs, especially Inari, Finland, Nuuk, Greenland, and the Arctic youth scenarios, the **indigenous issues** were heavily raised in the future scenarios. Mostly in the positive scenarios there was seen a better position of indigenous peoples in the hubs, involving them to decision-making, and supporting their cultures and the continuation of traditional knowledge. In the positive scenarios, where indigenous peoples and cultures were strongly taken into account, the position of indigenous peoples was very good, and the whole area was proud of them, creating a cultural hub to the region, like in Inari and Varanger. In many of the scenarios, however, it was pointed out, that there is a fear that the position of indigenous people will be further weakened, and that other livelihoods, like tourism and mining, will take over the land used by indigenous peoples for traditional livelihoods. This was especially pointed out in Nuuk, and in the Arctic Youth scenarios. This is feared to cause not only the diminishing of these traditional livelihoods and knowledge, but also severe mental issues to the indigenous communities. In addition, it was seen important to educate the tourists about indigenous cultures, also by integrating the culture to tourism, and offer genuine experiences. The conflicts on land use were also raised in the scenarios, where they are feared to escalate in the future, but in the more positive scenarios, the use of more participatory methods and

involving locals is hoped to resolve the conflicts on land use, resulting in good balance, and harmonious relationships between different stakeholders, indigenous peoples, and locals. In the scenarios it is clear, that the voices of the locals must be heard in decision-making, and local knowledge is crucial in land use planning, also because they have the best knowledge of the area. In Nuuk, however, there was a need for inviting external investors to develop tourism industry and infrastructure, but there was also pointed out a fear that the entrepreneurs in the tourism industry are dominated by Danish newcomers. Climate change was seen to have many impacts on the traditional livelihoods, knowledge, and the culture of indigenous peoples, and this was mentioned for example in Inari, Nuuk and the Arctic Youth scenarios.

The **new technology development and innovations** were pointed out in many scenarios as a positive driver for the future. In the future, new technology is hoped to combat the challenges, for example in transport and energy production, and to provide less impact on the environment than the current technology. It was seen to help the problems and reduce the carbon footprint for example from transport (Westfjords), and vessels used in aquaculture (Varanger), and also to create resource efficient forestry (i.e Lean forestry). However, as stated in the forestry scenarios, the technological advances can increasingly supplement human workers in the future, and lead to increase in energy consumption. The increasing consumption was heavily pointed out in the Arctic Youth scenarios, where that was a key driver in the future. The Arctic Youth saw that the solution to those problems is only to reduce consumption. In some of the positive scenarios like from the forestry scenarios and the Arctic Youth, the demand for environmentally friendly products has led to improved raw material efficiency, and effective recycling, which has reduced the need for new energy sources.

The **energy perspectives** were seen important in many scenarios, especially because of the geopolitical situation in Europe. The self-sufficiency in energy was seen ideal in the positive scenarios, but in many scenarios, it was seen important to be low-carbon. Overall, the situation in the geopolitics is seen to cause continuous instability in the energy production, stated in the forestry scenarios. Green transition was pointed out in many of the scenarios, but especially in the forestry scenario it was one of the most dominant drivers, helping in self-sufficiency, in reducing carbon footprint in different sectors, and energy supply. Also, the use and development of other energy modes, like hydropower, wind power, and small-scale energy production, but also the swift to alternative fuels like hydrogen were pointed out in the positive scenarios. The new modes of energy and the green transition was mentioned also

in the forestry scenarios to have increasing effect on disputes and conflicts, especially between those who gain and loose.

The **new geopolitical situation** was seen to also have positive impacts for example by new public investments in defense, creating local ripple effects, jobs, and new transport lines and cooperation with for example Finland and Sweden. The negative part is seen to be the frozen situation and lack of people-to-people collaboration with Russia.

The **swift from industrialism to consumerism**, and the increased demand for energy and resources mentioned in the Arctic Youth scenarios were seen to have impacts on the economic uncertainty, and cause conflicts. The new situation was also mentioned in the scenarios by creating aspects in investment in defense, creating jobs, and new transport lines, for example between Finland and Sweden. The self-sufficiency in locally produced renewable energy among other things means, that there is a great need for both social and technological innovation.

In most of the scenarios, **employment** was seen as a positive impact of different scenarios, where the work opportunities are seen to be better by new industries, technology, and growing tourism. The human migration to and from the Arctic, was pointed out in many scenarios, and in some scenarios, there was still the effect of people moving away from the remote areas in search of better opportunities, and hence causing a lack of skilled workforce. The depopulation was seen to have harmful effects to the whole area by reducing the services and infrastructure and getting less workforce resulting in the worse economy.

But as especially brought up in the Arctic Youth scenarios, there might be climate-induced migration towards the Arctic. The availability of workforce is also related to the competency of the area. The competence and the ability to get workforce is seen to be related to the accessibility at least in some hubs, like in Westfjords and Suđuroy. In some scenarios, the lack of workforce is seen to be compensated by the foreign actors in the future, but this is not seen as a positive thing in all of the scenarios. This is because local knowledge is needed, and also because of the problems brought by multiculturalism. In addition, the social license to operate (SLO), indigenous rights on land, and effects on biodiversity, are in some scenarios seen to cause reduced development in certain areas. To combat the availability of work force, and to get the young people to stay in the hubs, the reliefs for young people was introduced for example in Varanger and Arctic Youth to help with taxation, or student loans.

4.5. The concrete steps and responsible parties needed for reaching the desirable futures

In the overall evaluation of the scenarios, the evaluators identified the following issues as the most important concrete steps towards desirable futures:

* **Knowledge-based planning** for sustainable development, especially within the tourism industry, as it is essential to align tourism activities with specific and desired local development objectives. Knowledge-based planning includes carrying out carrying capacity analyses, establishing regulations and implementing monitoring mechanisms to ensure the preservation of a clean and diverse natural environment. Knowledge-based planning is also essential for responsible land use.

* More **cross-sectoral analysis** of the gains and losses of different activities and long-term planning accordingly. This should be done by setting a concrete, joint and mutually agreed 'mission' (goal) towards which planning would lead.

* **Empowering local communities** and strengthening local identities involves promoting awareness of local traditions, local food sources to foster local pride and local consumption patterns. It also means ensuring that a fair share of the value added from extractive industries stays locally and benefits local people. Industries such as tourism should be developed in dialogue and in line with local values, histories and aspirations. In addition, strengthening local decision-making processes and encouraging participation in extractive industries should be integral aspects of empowering local communities.

* **Transparency and inclusive decision making.** Although we know that resource use is a win-win situation, if local people are involved in decision making and understand the nuances of the trade-offs, they will have a better understanding of the choices being made and there may be less conflict.

* **Addressing demographic challenges,** creating diverse employment opportunities in remote areas, developing attractive housing options and accessible education in Arctic hub environments.

Looking at the evaluations of concrete steps in the Hub regions, similar themes emerge, but with different weighting in different regions and Hubs. Table 3 summarises these differences.

Table 3. Topics of concrete steps needed in different hub regions. **Green** = strong emphasis, **yellow** = medium emphasis, **blue** = mentioned.

	Inari, FI	Malå, SE	Nuuk, GL	Suðuroy, FO	Varanger, NO	Westfjords, IS
Access, transportation				Yellow		Green
Circular economy		Yellow		Blue		
Education possibilities (esp indigenous cultures and languages)	Green	Blue	Yellow			Yellow
Infrastructure		Yellow				Green
Investments, business development, marketing	Yellow	Green				Green
Local participation, increased cooperation	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow		Blue
Management and planning actions	Blue	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow		
Public policy actions		Blue		Blue	Green	Yellow
Regulations (tourism, aquaculture)	Yellow		Green	Green	Blue	
Technology development (e.g. AI)		Green				
Work opportunities						Green

It seems that for the Westfjords area in Iceland as well as for Suðuroy in the Faroe Islands, issues such as road infrastructure and accessibility of all kinds are extremely important to be addressed. In the scenario work in Nuuk in Greenland, but also in the Faroe Islands, the need for regulation and management is strongly emphasised. For the Faroe Islands, the most urgent need for regulation concerned access to nature. The evaluations of the youth workshop also focused on regulations concerning migration, tourism, and access to nature. Remote working and improving accessibility were also seen as necessary concrete actions. In the indigenous hubs of Inari, Finland, and Nuuk, Greenland, the need for education in indigenous languages and about indigenous cultures is mentioned.

Most hub regions emphasise the involvement of local people. The establishment of working groups, local meeting places or other local bodies is seen as a concrete solution. The evaluation of Malå in Sweden suggests the implementation of the working model "Conversation - Consensus - Interaction - Cooperation" at all levels and between practice and science/research. When evaluating the concrete steps to achieve a positive outcome in Forestry Future, management and planning actions come to the fore. Local participation is also seen as a necessity.

4.1. Responsible actors and parties in society to make the changes and decisions for desired Arctic futures

The selection of possible responsible actors is naturally restricted. Thus, the mentions such as decision-makers on various levels is repeated in many of the evaluations. However, also local community's role was emphasised as an active party. The role of business and industrial sector is interesting: its social responsibility is often emphasised and the sector is seen as a responsible party which in addition has strong influence on decision-makers.

Here are the responsible actors mentioned in the evaluations with some justifications:

- **Local community** and its inhabitants
 - By voting for decision-makers and in demanding changes
 - In Westfjords two municipalities are merging and this view relates to the change: "Whole community should be responsible for making the changes about the development of communities involved. Even though local councilors might in the end make decisions, a consultation forum for inhabitants must be established. At national level this must be supported, that must recognize the importance of bringing the power to the people, which of course will operate in the frame of laws and regulations." (Westfjords)

- Local communities and businesses in the Arctic are directly impacted by changes in land use, tourism, and economic activities. They should actively engage in sustainable practices, support community initiatives (Youth evaluation)
- Indigenous communities and their leaders hold significant knowledge about the Arctic's ecosystems and traditional practices. Their involvement is crucial for ensuring that decisions align with cultural values, and they should actively participate in the decision-making processes that impact their lands and livelihoods. (Youth evaluation)
- **Increased cross-sectoral cooperation:**
 - Strong demand in Nuuk, Greenland, to ensure holistic development: “Tourism development must take a holistic approach in which economic, nature and environmental, social and cultural considerations are treated equally. Tourism development balances between cultural conservation and cultural development, as well as nature conservation and nature exploitation. In this way, a tourism industry is created that promotes healthy environments and creates good lives.”
- **Governmental bodies:** municipalities, regional and national governments
 - Must have the ability to plan and decide for the future to the best for the society
 - From a Suðuroy perspective in the Faroe Islands, the feeling of political decision affecting the island being taken elsewhere is prominent, but local tradition as well as innovation is also a strong force. Depending on the situation and context, decision-makers at all levels are responsible for contributing to policy-making that will lead to desirable futures.
- **Business sector and industrial sector:**
 - When it comes to taking responsibility for the spill-over effects on the community and environment resulting from their resource extractions. They also have a central role in terms of setting the agenda and being a role model for future business initiatives and local entrepreneurship.
 - The private sector and resource extraction companies have a crucial role in the desired future of the arctic. Aside from being one of the most powerful actors, they have a lot of influence in local, regional and national governance. They also have the resources - money and human capital to promote their agenda.
 - In forestry, forest management and forestry companies: new adaptive methods combining wood production, climate adaptation and maintaining biodiversity and joint production of various uses of forests (collaboration), 2) CO2-binding in all steps of wood-based circular economy, 3) collaboration in

land-use planning with indigenous and local societies and forest based livelihoods (reindeer herding, tourism, berry industry etc) and participation of all relevant interest groups in land-use, 4) openness, transparency, information, willingness to hear values and concerns of all interest groups, understanding concerns hiding in positions.

- Businesses should adopt responsible business models that contribute to the well-being of both people and the environment. (Youth evaluation)
- **Research institutions:**
 - Research institutions have their responsibility in making desirable changes through developing relevant research that examines the complex interplay between local and global drivers, and which enlightens local needs and situations. Research institutes play a key role in providing evidence-based information to decision-makers and stakeholders in the Arctic hub context.
- **Human agency:**
 - Human agency - as government and businesses respond to the pulse of the public if it benefits them, if local community and the public at large demand changes then it can also be possible that they influence where the future of the Arctic is going.

5. Conclusions

In the ArcticHubs scenario processes, the aim was to build scenarios based on expert knowledge from local to national perspectives in a situation where there are different interests for land use. Imagining futures can create preparedness for the future by identifying opportunities and addressing threats in the operational environment. It should be noted that circumstances vary from region to region and, for example, the relevant scenarios constructed in this project consist of very original settings in each area. However, such alternative scenario information produced by the Hubs can be further used to interact and advise actors and policy makers at local, regional and national levels in a forward-looking way.

From a methodological point of view, we used a mixed methods approach in which expert surveys, participatory workshops (both online and face-to-face), scenario planning and individual interviews and evaluation questions played a key role. Together these form the ArcticHubs scenario planning process.

The content of the evaluation process showed that there are issues that are common to all hub regions. Although it is obvious that the hubs of the vast area differ from each other, among the common issues are climate change with both positive and negative impacts; increasing consumption including various aspects such as green transition, technology, resource use and pollution; and demographic changes covering both migration to and from the Arctic. These were all identified as key drivers.

Nature and the environment, new innovations and technologies, sustainable lifestyles and reduced consumption, resolving conflicts, making local voices heard and increasing public participation in decision-making were themes that raised hopes, while concerns were related to the shortcomings of these themes. Promoting the position of indigenous peoples was also an important aspect of desirable futures.

Maritime Hubs have different drivers and scenarios than inland Hubs, for example transport and access are crucial to the future of these regions. In addition, the situation in Nuuk is very different from other Hubs as it is more isolated and people have to look for opportunities outside the island, which is not as compulsory as in northern Scandinavia, for example.

There were also differences in the views of the Youth Future Forum compared to others, as young people emphasised more the need to reduce consumption. Young people were also more concerned about climate change than some other groups.

Concrete actions are needed in different areas of life, from educational opportunities to management and planning practices. One of the most important and widely shared actions would be to involve local communities in all land use in the Hub regions. In terms of responsible actors, it is clear that public bodies, authorities and decision-makers have the greatest role to play, but local communities themselves were also seen as important actors.

The business and industrial sector was also seen as an important actor from a sustainability perspective, not only in terms of its actions but also in terms of its power to influence decision-makers.

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